

Are beaches accessible to all? Economic valuation and mapping of recreational ecosystem services for wheelchair users in Greece

Valentini Stamatiadou^{a,*}, Antonios D. Mazaris^b, Theodoros Chalazas^a, Adonis F. Velegrakis^a, Stelios Katsanevakis^a

^a Department of Marine Sciences, University of the Aegean, Mytilene 81100, Greece

^b Department of Ecology, School of Biology, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Accessibility
Disability
Ecosystem service
Coast
Monetary
Spatial Planning

ABSTRACT

Individuals with mobility impairments frequently face significant barriers to participating in coastal recreational activities, primarily due to inadequate infrastructure and poor maintenance. This study evaluates the needs and behaviors of wheelchair users to estimate the economic value of beach recreation for this group in Greece. By combining economic valuation methods with accessibility analysis, we estimate that beach recreation for wheelchair users generates approximately €237 million annually. However, existing accessibility barriers result in an estimated annual loss of €57 million. Our spatial analysis reveals that beaches equipped with accessibility infrastructure yield an average annual value of €92,611 per beach, compared to €42,374 for those without such facilities. On average, the recreational value for wheelchair users across Greek beaches is €62,206 per hectare per year. Notably, only 11 % of access ramps (n = 322) include all essential accessibility features, such as designated disabled parking. These findings underscore the need for targeted infrastructure improvements, providing policymakers with actionable insights to foster inclusive tourism, enhance social equity, and support economically and socially sustainable coastal management.

1. Introduction

Disability is a multifaceted condition that often leads to exclusion and creates barriers that prevent individuals from participating in various aspects of life [1], including healthcare [1], employment [2,3], transportation [4], access to information [5], and leisure activities [6–8]. In Europe, approximately 101 million people – one in four individuals – experience some form of disability, although only 30 million have a formally recognized disability [9]. Projections suggest that these numbers will continue to rise in the coming decades, driven by population ageing and the increased likelihood of disability with advancing age [10,11]. Despite the widespread social and economic implications of disability, accessibility challenges persist and vary significantly between countries.

According to the World Health Organization, “accessibility” refers to the extent to which an environment, service, or product accommodates the widest possible range of individuals, including those with disabilities [12]. Many beaches present accessibility challenges due to inadequate infrastructure, such as the absence of ramps, accessible pathways, and

designated disabled parking [7]. These deficiencies limit individuals’ ability to engage with natural spaces and to benefit from the physical, mental, and social advantages associated with such interactions [6,13,14]. Consequently, these barriers can contribute to discrimination, hinder equal participation in social and economic life, and increase the risk of social isolation [9].

Coastal recreation and related activities are key components of cultural ecosystem services, offering essential benefits to individuals and society. Therefore, numerous studies have attempted to quantify these benefits in monetary terms [15–18]. However, fewer have focused on mapping ecosystem services [19,20], and even fewer have mapped their economic value [21–23]. Notably, there is a significant gap in research specifically focused on cultural ecosystem services for individuals with disabilities [24]. Existing studies concerning people with mobility impairments and beach recreation have primarily explored user perspectives [7,14] or preferences [25], developed methodological tools [6,26], examined spatial patterns [27], created technological applications [28], and assessed accessibility through quantitative indicators [29]. To the best of our knowledge, the economic value of beach recreation for

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: valentini.stamatiadou@gmail.com (V. Stamatiadou).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2025.106805>

Received 4 November 2024; Received in revised form 15 April 2025; Accepted 11 June 2025

Available online 24 June 2025

0308-597X/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

wheelchair users has not yet been studied or spatially mapped. Incorporating ecosystem service frameworks and participatory processes—such as monetary valuation—can support shared understanding among stakeholders and provide essential information for inclusive spatial planning and environmental management [30–32].

The issue of beach accessibility is particularly important for Greece, due to its significance for both residents and the large number of domestic and international tourists it attracts. Approximately 18.2 % of the Greek population lives with some form of disability or serious health condition [33], with an estimated 328,000 to 550,000 individuals experiencing mobility impairments [34,35]. Greece's extensive coastline, which offers a wide range of ecosystem services, including recreation, is a vital part of the country's culture, identity, and everyday life. Additionally, Greece is one of Europe's leading tourist destinations, welcoming around 29 million visitors annually, primarily for "sun and beach" tourism [36]. Across Europe, an estimated 70 % of people with disabilities have both the financial means and physical ability to travel. It is estimated that tourism by people with disabilities contributes over €80 billion to the European economy, including expenditures by accompanying friends, relatives, and caregivers [10]. Therefore, beach accessibility is a key issue not only for the well-being of local communities but also for the sustainability of the tourism sector, the national economy, and broader goals of social inclusion and equality.

In this context, the study aimed to develop and apply a comprehensive framework for valuing and mapping the recreational ecosystem service of beaches for wheelchair users in Greece. This was accomplished through four key steps: (1) collecting data on the attitudes, habits, and preferences of wheelchair users; (2) documenting the locations of special access ramps and related accessibility infrastructures; (3) estimating the economic value of beach recreation for this user group; and (4) conducting a spatial analysis of this value based on specific beach features. The findings highlight the critical importance of accessibility infrastructure for wheelchair users, reveal the substantial recreational value associated with accessible coastal environments, and demonstrate notable spatial variations in value, largely influenced by differences in beach features.

2. Methodology

The value of the recreational ecosystem service provided by Greek beaches for wheelchair users was estimated by calculating both the direct use values and the option value derived from the coast [37]. Additionally, the potential value lost by individuals who are unable to visit the beach due to insufficient or poorly maintained accessibility infrastructure was assessed. A cost-benefit analysis was conducted to evaluate whether the benefits of installing new ramps and related infrastructure outweigh the associated costs, based on two alternative scenarios. The spatial mapping of this ecosystem service across Greek beaches was carried out using a hierarchical approach that considered three key criteria: the presence of accessibility ramps, the availability of additional access infrastructure, and the annual visitation rate, which was estimated through crowdsourced methods.

2.1. Monetary valuation

The *Recreational Value for Wheelchair Users (RVW_u)* was evaluated by considering two components: *Domestic Tourism (DT)*, which included expenditures during beach visits and travel costs, and *Accessibility_{Domestic} (A_D)* calculated as the *Willingness To Pay (WTP)* of Greek wheelchair users for improving beach accessibility. *DT* represented the direct use value, while *A_D* represented the option value of this ecosystem service [37].

$$RVW_u \left(\frac{\text{€}}{\text{yr}} \right) = \text{Direct Use Value} + \text{Option Value} = DT + A_D \quad (1)$$

To calculate Eq. 1, distinct equations were formulated for each component, as detailed below. Data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed to organizations and associations that support and engage wheelchair users, supplemented with available national data. The survey was conducted between March and June 2024 and required a minimum sample size of 83 responses, based on an estimated population of ~108,000 wheelchair users (the estimation process is explained in the following paragraph), with a 95 % confidence level and a 5.5 % margin of error [38].

Following the guidelines for developing questionnaires provided by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) [39], the survey consisted of four sections, Table S1. The first section focused on individuals' beach habits, expenditures, and preferred beach features. The second section sought opinions on accessibility and motivations to visit a beach. The third section explored participants' willingness to financially contribute to improving Greek beach accessibility. The fourth section examined the social, economic, and demographic profiles of the survey participants. Data from the first, third, and fourth sections were subsequently used in the formulation of the corresponding equations:

$$\text{Domestic Tourism} \left(\frac{\text{€}}{\text{yr}} \right) =$$

$$\text{Population}_{\text{yes, } WU} * [(Trips_{\text{overnight}} * Cost_{Trips_{\text{overnight}}}) + (Trips_{\text{daily}} * Cost_{Trips_{\text{daily}}})] \quad (2)$$

Where *Population_{yes, WU}* represents the number of wheelchair users in Greece who visit beaches, calculated as the proportion of the total wheelchair user population who reported engaging in beach visits. As contemporary and validated statistics on the number of wheelchair users in Greece were not available from national or EU sources, relevant information was derived from the World Health Organization and the Hellenic Statistical Authority to estimate the population of wheelchair users [40,41]. Based on these sources, it was estimated that there are ~108,000 individuals in Greece who use wheelchairs (= *Population_{WU}*), assuming that 1 % of the global population uses a wheelchair [40], and given that the total Greek population is 10,816,286 individuals [41]. The proportion of survey respondents who reported visiting Greek beaches was then multiplied by this estimate to calculate *Population_{yes, WU} * Trips_{overnight}* was the average number of overnight trips for recreation in Greek beaches annually, *Cost_{Trips_{overnight}}* was the average cost per overnight trip, *Trips_{daily}* was the average number of daily visits to Greek beaches annually, and *Cost_{Trips_{daily}}* was the average cost per daily trip, including both expenditures at the beach and travel costs.

$$\text{Accessibility}_{\text{Domestic}} (A_D, \text{€}/\text{yr}) = \text{Willingness To Pay} * (\text{Population}_{WU}) \quad (3)$$

Willingness To Pay (WTP) was estimated using the Contingent Valuation Method [23] with a single-bounded dichotomous choice format, analyzed through a logistic regression model. Respondents were first presented with a scenario outlining the lack of beach accessibility infrastructure, without any initial monetary value to minimize strategic, informational, and starting-point biases. They were then randomly assigned one of five bid amounts (€10, €25, €50, €100, or €200) and asked if they would be willing to pay this annual amount as a tax contribution. Bid amounts were uniformly distributed across the sample to ensure balanced responses.

A logistic regression model was applied to the *WTP* responses using a backward stepwise elimination method. The dependent variable was the binary response (yes/no) to the proposed bid. Explanatory variables included demographic characteristics, perceptions of accessibility importance, attitudes toward inclusive infrastructure, behavioral patterns, and the bid amount. Variables were removed iteratively based on the Wald test, retaining only those with statistically significant effects.

Individuals who did not visit beaches due to insufficient infrastructure were asked to respond to questions assuming improved accessibility. This enabled the calculation of the lost use value, termed

Lost Domestic Tourism (LDT), according to the following equation.

$$\text{Lost Domestic Tourism} \left(\text{LDT}, \frac{\text{€}}{\text{yr}} \right) = \text{Population}_{\text{no_WU}} * \left(\left(E_{\text{Trips_overnight}} * E_{\text{Cost_overnight}} \right) + \left(E_{\text{Trips_daily}} * E_{\text{Cost_daily}} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

$\text{Population}_{\text{no_WU}}$ represents the number of wheelchair users in Greece who currently do not visit beaches. It was calculated by multiplying the proportion of survey respondents who reported not visiting beaches by the total estimated population of wheelchair users in Greece (108,000 individuals) [40,41]. $E_{\text{Trips_overnight}}$ denotes the estimated average number of overnight trips to Greek beaches that these individuals would take annually, assuming improved accessibility. Under the same hypothetical scenario $E_{\text{Cost_overnight}}$ refers to the estimated average cost per overnight trip. $E_{\text{Trips_daily}}$ represents the estimated average number of daily beach visits per year, and, and $E_{\text{Cost_daily}}$ indicates the estimated average cost per daily visit, including both beach-related expenditures and travel costs.

A comparative cost-benefit analysis was conducted to evaluate the financial implications of investing in new ramps and accessibility infrastructure. Two approaches were applied to estimate the benefits: (a) the annual visitation expenditures (€/yr) of individuals who currently visit beaches, and (b) the estimated annual visitation expenditures (€/yr) of individuals who do not currently visit beaches for recreational purposes but would if accessibility were improved (based on Eq. 4). These approaches were contextualized relative to the total estimated population of 108,000 wheelchair users. For costs, we used installation expenses based on estimates provided by the European Commission and the Greek Ministry of Tourism under the "Creation of Integrated Tourist Accessible Marine Destinations" initiative, which estimates €70,000 per beach for the installation of accessibility infrastructure [42].

2.2. Mapping

To map the recreational value of Greek beaches for wheelchair users, the following steps were undertaken:

Step 1. A geospatial vector file was constructed to illustrate the locations of access ramps and related infrastructure. Facility data were obtained from the companies Seatrac^a and Seaccess,^b which design and install these infrastructures. Buffer zones around each ramp were defined based on respondents' feedback from the questionnaire regarding their maximum comfortable movement distance around accessibility ramps.

Step 2. Spatial data for Greek beaches were sourced from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, specifically Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use 2018 (vector) [43]. This dataset (consisted of polygons) includes all Greek beaches meeting a minimum mapping unit of 0.5 ha and a minimum width of 10 m. Beaches with accessibility infrastructure not meeting these criteria were manually added using Google Maps.

Step 3. A second geospatial vector file was created to map the visitation index. Visitation was estimated using geotagged flickr^c photos [44]. These crowdsourced data were cross-referenced with the geographic coordinates of each beach. The average number of photos near each beach uploaded annually (between 2005 and 2022) was used to calculate the visitation index (photos/beach/year), serving as a proxy for recreational activity.

Step 4. A divisive hierarchical approach was applied to assign recreational ecosystem service values to each beach, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The total economic value of recreational services for wheelchair users

(RVW_u) was distributed across beaches using the outputs of the previous steps and data collected from the questionnaire.

Initially, the RVW_u was allocated based on the presence or absence of access infrastructure. Survey participants indicated how frequently they visit beaches with and without such facilities, allowing the estimation of visitation preferences, used to proportionally allocate values.

Next, value allocation was refined by considering the presence of facilities, including (a) access ramps, (b) disabled parking, (c) accessible toilets, (d) adapted changing rooms, (e) shaded areas, and (f) accessible showers. Respondents reported how often they visited beaches with each type of infrastructure, which allowed the estimation of infrastructure-specific visitation rates. These values were used to further distribute the RVW_u among beaches equipped with accessibility features.

Finally, we calculated visitation indices for wheelchair users at beaches based on infrastructure type, using Flickr data. Beaches could belong to multiple categories if they featured more than one type of facility. For each beach, the proportion of photos relative to the total number of photos within its category was calculated and normalized (ranging from 0 to 1), ensuring that the sum across all beaches equaled 1. These normalized values were then used to assign a proportion of the RVW_u to each beach, reflecting both infrastructure presence and visitation rates. Beaches with multiple types of infrastructure had their values aggregated accordingly (e.g., a beach with both access ramps and disabled parking received a combined value). The sum of all assigned values equaled the total RVW_u .

The recreational value for each beach was normalized by its area to obtain per-hectare estimates in euros per year (€/ha/yr).

Spatial analyses were performed using ArcMap 10.8 and QGIS 3.22.7. Data analyses for Eqs. 1–4 were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 28.0.1, Stata 14.2, and Excel.

3. Results

3.1. Profile of wheelchair users

A total of 91 questionnaires were collected, with 53 responses from men and 38 from women. Respondents ranged in age range from 15 to 70, with the largest group (38.5 %) aged 41–50. The majority or participants (41.8 %) held a master's degree, and the most common monthly income range (28.6 %) was €1001–€1500 per month.

Most respondents (89 %) reported visiting beaches for recreational purposes; however, 11 % stated that they do not visit beaches due to inadequate or lacking accessibility infrastructure. The primary motivations for visiting beaches included "relaxation" (67 %), "exercise" (59 %), and the "therapeutic effects" of the coastal environment (55 %), all of which were associated with both mental and physical health. Despite 83 % of the responders rating accessibility as "very important" (Fig. 2b) and 82 % believing that improved access would have a positive impact on their lives (Fig. 2d), the majority (63.5 %) rated current beach accessibility as "very bad" or "bad" (Fig. 2a). Notably, 60.2 % of respondents reported having "frequent" or "constant" interaction with nature (Fig. 2c).

In response to the prompt "For me, the accessibility of the beaches means..." participants most frequently cited terms such as "equality" (27.5 %), "freedom" (24.2 %), "quality of life", "autonomy", and "right" (Fig. 2f). Reflecting these values, 60.2 % of respondents reported actively advocating for improved beach accessibility on a "frequent" or "constant" basis (Fig. 2e).

3.2. Accessibility facilities on Greek beaches

The collected data revealed that out of the 2573 beaches mapped across Greece, 322 beaches (12 %) were equipped with special access ramps for individuals with mobility impairments. The total area of the mapped beaches amounted to 10,448 ha, ranging from very small

^a <https://seatrac.gr/>

^b <https://sea-access.gr/>

^c <https://www.flickr.com/>

Fig. 1. A divisive hierarchical approach was applied to allocate recreational value to each beach, based on its accessibility features and visitation rates. At the first level, beaches were categorized by the presence or absence of access infrastructure, and *RVWu* value was distributed according to the percentage of visitation preference for each category. The second level considered the presence of specific accessibility features, such as special access ramps, parking for disabled users, accessible toilets, adapted changing rooms, shaded areas, and accessible showers. Values were allocated based on visitation preferences for each type of infrastructure. At the third level, visitation indices for each infrastructure type, as well as for beaches without accessibility features, were calculated using flickr data. These indices were then used to assign an economic value to each beach (€/beach/yr), which was subsequently divided by the beach area to calculate the final value per hectare (€/ha/yr).

beaches of just 0.01 ha (classified as pocket beaches) to larger ones reaching up to 158 ha. There were notable variations in coastal geomorphology, with some beaches consisting of fine sand and others of coarser sand or pebbles. Bathymetric differences were also observed, with some coastlines exhibiting steep slopes and others more gradual inclination. These physical characteristics significantly affect both the type of infrastructure needed and the level of accessibility provided to wheelchair users, depending on their specific mobility needs.

Among the 322 accessible beaches, 165 offered disabled parking, 62 had accessible toilets, 79 included adapted changing rooms, 72 provided adapted shaded areas, and 121 had accessible showers. Beach facilities were distributed as follows: 42 % of sites had only a special ramp, 17 %

had the ramp plus one additional feature, 12 % included two features, 9 % had three, 8 % had four, and 11 % offered all specified amenities. Fig. 3 presents the spatial distribution of these infrastructures across regions, highlighting a mismatch between the availability of accessibility features and the actual needs of both local residents and tourists.

For instance, Attica-Athens (Fig. 3, region I), with a population of 3.8 million and €3.3 billion in tourist revenue from May to September 2023, had only 48 ramps, indicating significant accessibility gaps. Similarly, Central Macedonia (Fig. 3, region b), with a population of 1.8 million, had just 17 ramps, despite €1.4 billion in summer tourist revenues in 2023. The Ionian Islands (Fig. 3, region e), serving a population of 204,532 and having 15 ramps, also demonstrated insufficient

Fig. 2. Summary statistics on the attitudes, needs, and recreational behavior of wheelchair users regarding beach recreation in Greece.

accessibility infrastructure to serve the high number of tourists, contributing €2 billion to the economy in 2023.

3.3. Monetary estimation of recreational value of wheelchair users

3.3.1. Domestic tourism value

The *Domestic Tourism value* (€/yr) was estimated using Eq. 1 at €229 million/yr (95 % CI: €114–349 million/yr) for the 89 % of Greece’s 108,000 wheelchair users who reported visiting beaches. Based on our analytical framework, the average annual expenditure per individual for beach visits was estimated at €1382/yr (95 % CI: €936–1952/yr), derived from an average of 23 visits per year (95 % CI: 17–30), with average daily expenses of €28 (95 % CI: €22–33) for beach-related costs and €41 (95 % CI: €32–51) for travel.

Additionally, the average annual expenditure for beach leisure trips in Greece was estimated at €998/yr (95 % CI: €564–1673/yr), based on an average of 2.4 trips per year (95 % CI: 1.7–3.4), with each trip costing approximately €367 (95 % CI: €291–460).

The option value, *Accessibility_{Domestic}* (€/year), was estimated at €7.8

million (95 % CI: €875,000–14 million/yr) for the total population of wheelchair users (n = 108,000 individuals). This was based on the estimated WTP of €73 per person annually (95 % CI: €8–137), with 46 % of respondents indicating a willingness to financially support accessibility improvements. Logistic regression analysis identified accessibility, frequency of interaction with nature, and bid amounts as statistically significant or marginally significant predictors, Table 1. Positive responses were more likely when respondents valued accessibility highly and engaged regularly with nature, and less likely at higher bid amounts.

The total estimated recreational value for wheelchair users RVW_{it} was €237 million/yr, with *Domestic Tourism* accounting for 96 % and the *Accessibility_{Domestic}* (option value) component for the remaining 4 %.

3.3.2. Lost domestic tourism (LDT)

Respondents who reported not visiting beaches were asked about their likely behavior if accessible beaches were available near their residences. Based on these responses and Eq. 4, the lost value was estimated at €57 million/yr (95 % CI: €20–116 million), representing 11 %

Fig. 3. The accessibility index reflects the number of facilities, adjusted for the population size of individuals with ambulatory difficulties in each region. The color scale (from yellow to dark purple) indicates relative accessibility levels, with darker shades representing higher accessibility. Blue bubbles denote the presence of accessibility infrastructure, and their size corresponds to the diversity of available facilities (e.g., access ramps, disabled parking, accessible showers, changing rooms, shaded areas, and toilets). Neon yellow columns represent inbound tourism revenue during the peak “sun and beach” season (May–September), highlighting the growing demand for accessible coastal destinations among tourists with mobility impairments.

of the total population of wheelchair users. These individuals reported that they would spend an average of €3297 annually (95 % CI: €1155 - 6880) on daily beach visits, with an average of 32 visits per year (95 % CI: 14–60). Each visit would cost approximately €26 (95 % CI: €18–36) for beach costs and €65 (95 % CI: €42–93) for travel. Additionally, respondents indicated they would spend an average of €1500 (95 % CI: €540–2899) on beach leisure trips, with an estimated 2.5 trips per year

(95 % CI: 1.3–3.9), at an average cost of €490 per trip (95 % CI: €310–680).

3.3.3. Cost-benefit analysis

The comparative cost-benefit analysis demonstrated that the benefits of implementing new accessibility infrastructure outweigh the associated costs in both scenarios, [Table 2](#). In the first scenario (based on

Table 1
Estimated parameters and statistics for the dichotomous choice model.

Variable	Explanation	Coef.	S.E.	z	p-value
Accessibility (Table S1, Variable B2)	The relative importance you ascribe to coastal accessibility.	0.766	0.404	1.9	0.058
Nature (Table S1, Variable B3)	The frequency of contact with the natural environment.	0.369	0.198	1.9	0.062
Bid (Table S1, Variable Bid)	Amount proposed in WTP question.	-0.008	0.003	-2.4	0.016
Constant	-	-4.538	2.092	-2.2	0.030
Number Obs.:	91				
Log likelihood	-56.27				
Pseudo R-squared:	0.10				

current beachgoer’s behavior), the projected economic contribution would be sufficient to support the installation of approximately 234 accessibility ramps. In the second scenario (including potential new beachgoers), the potential economic contribution could finance the installation of up to 560 ramps.

3.4. Mapping the estimated recreational value of Greek beaches for wheelchair users (RVWu)

Respondents indicated that 60 % of their annual beach visits were to beaches with accessibility infrastructure. The functional zone of influence for each access ramp was estimated at ~70 m. Survey-based preference frequencies for infrastructure types revealed that 23 % of the selected locations featured access ramps, 19 % had disabled parking, 14 % had accessible showers, 15 % had accessible toilets, 12 % provided adapted changing rooms, and 17 % offered adapted shaded areas. In the fourth step of the mapping process, values were allocated based on the visitation index for each combination of features.

The distribution of recreational value (RVW_u: €237 million/yr) is presented in Table 3 (based on beach features) and Figs. 4 and 5 as spatially distributed values in €/beach/yr. The highest estimated value at a single accessible location was €4.8 million per beach per year, observed at a beach with adapted shaded areas and particularly high visitation rates. The average value for beaches equipped with one or more types of accessibility infrastructure was €92,611 per beach per year, while beaches without any infrastructure had an average value of €42,374 per beach per year.

The highest estimated value per beach was €18.7 million per year, observed on a highly frequented small beach (approximately 1 ha in size) located on the island of Crete, which is equipped with all types of access infrastructure, Fig. 5. The average estimated value across Greek beaches was €62,206/ha/yr, with values ranging from approximately €0 to €18 million/ha/yr, Figure S1. The regions of Crete, Rhodes, and Attica–Athens are presented as representative case studies within the broader study area, Fig. 5 and Figure S2, with total estimated annual values of €78 million (mean: €293,852/beach/yr; €140,772/ha/yr), €16 million (mean: €302,323/beach/yr; €124,175/ha/yr), and €17 million (mean: €94,202/beach/yr; €107,900/ha/yr), respectively.

Table 2
Comparison of the benefits and costs associated with installing comprehensive accessibility infrastructure (including facilities such as ramps, designated disabled parking, and other key features). Benefits are based on daily expenditures by current beachgoers (individuals who currently visit the beach) and potential beachgoers (individuals who do not visit due to accessibility barriers). Costs represent the estimated expenses for installing all required accessibility infrastructure at a single location.

	Expenses-Daily Visits (€/yr)	Population with ambulatory difficulties	Benefits	Cost Ramp	Number-Access Ramps
Beachgoers	€1382 (95 % CI, 936–1952)	11 % *108,162	€16 million	70,000	234
Potential beachgoers	€3297 (95 % CI, 1155–6880)	= 11,897	€32 million		560

4. Discussion

Coastal ecosystems offer a wide range of ecosystem services, including recreation, that significantly contribute to human well-being [45]. However, individuals with mobility impairments often face barriers that limit their access to these benefits. This study demonstrates that such accessibility limitations contribute to both social and spatial inequalities. By offering an economic valuation and spatial mapping of recreational ecosystem services for wheelchair users, our findings highlight the urgent need for inclusive infrastructure and offer valuable insights to inform more effective and equitable coastal management strategies.

Greece, internationally recognized for its "sun and beach tourism", faces ongoing challenges in ensuring that its extensive coastline is accessible to all, particularly to wheelchair users. The recreational ecosystem services of Greek beaches are valued at approximately €21.4 billion annually [46]. Of this, an estimated €237 million, roughly 1 %, corresponds to the recreational value attributed to wheelchair users (RVWu). Although this group visits beaches less frequently than the general population, their associated costs are significantly higher, with an average expenditure of €60 per beach visit compared to €27 for the general population [46]. Annual spending among wheelchair users varies considerably, averaging €1382 (95 % CI: €936 to €1952) for day visits and €998 (95 % CI: €564 to €1673) for travel-related beach trips. This variation reflects not only differences between the general population but also substantial disparities within the group itself, driven by diverse needs. Some individuals require the assistance of a caregiver, others rent or use specialized equipment such as beach wheelchairs, and many either maintain a privately adapted vehicle or rely on costly accessible taxis due to the inaccessibility of most public transport. These elevated transportation and support-related expenses often result in overall costs that are more than twice those of other beachgoers. Moreover, the limited availability of accessible infrastructure, including adapted toilets and changing rooms, forces many visitors with mobility impairments to rely on nearby businesses to meet basic needs, further increasing the financial burden. These combined financial and infrastructural barriers are key factors contributing to the significantly lower visitation rates among wheelchair users. Our sample indicated that 11 % of wheelchair users do not visit the beach at all, and that overall visitation is estimated to be about half that of the general population.

Although still under-studied, accessible tourism holds significant potential for generating both social and economic benefits [47]. A 2012 survey indicated that demand for accessible tourism within the EU totaled 17.6 million trips, including 7.2 million by people with disabilities and 10.4 million by older individuals [48]. Despite this growing market, Greece has yet to fully embrace accessible tourism, which is expected to expand further due to increased life expectancy and a rising number of individuals with disabilities or mobility challenges. Improving beach accessibility presents a clear opportunity for Greece to strengthen its position in this sector. To effectively promote inclusive tourism, it is essential to update national statistics, conduct targeted surveys, and integrate stakeholder perspectives into the development of relevant policies and accessibility initiatives.

While 83 % of respondents rated accessibility as "very important" and emphasized strong motivations for beach visits related to mental and physical well-being, such as relaxation (67 %), exercise (59 %), and

Table 3

Distribution of the Recreational Value for Wheelchair users (RVWu) (€ / year), based on the three levels of the divisive hierarchical approach. Values in parentheses indicate the frequencies of the 1st and 2nd levels, as derived from questionnaire responses.

Recreational Value for Wheelchair Users (RVWu) (€/yr)	1st Level (type of beach) (€/yr)	2nd Level (Accessibility infrastructures) (€/yr)	3rd Level (visitation Index) (€/beach/yr)	
€ 237,084,521	with accessibility infrastructures (0.6)	special access ramps (0.23)	€ 142,250,713	min 858
			€ 32,717,663	max 1934,413
		disabled parking (0.19)	€ 27,027,635	mean 101,608
			€ 21,337,606	min 1668
		accessible toilets for wheelchair users (0.15)	€ 21,337,606	max 3758,888
			€ 21,337,606	mean 163,804
		adapted changing rooms (0.12)	€ 17,070,085	min 2273
			€ 17,070,085	max 5123,026
		adapted shade areas (0.17)	€ 24,182,621	mean 344,155
			€ 24,182,621	min 1735
		accessible showers (0.14)	€ 19,915,099	max 3910,557
			€ 19,915,099	mean 216,077
		Aggregation of all accessibility infrastructures per cell	€ 94,833,808	min 2671
			€ 94,833,808	max 4805,538
€ 94,833,808	mean 335,870			
€ 94,833,808	min 1237			
without accessibility infrastructures (0.4)	€ 94,833,808	€ 94,833,808	max 2788,287	
			mean 164,588	
			min ≈0	
without accessibility infrastructures (0.4)	€ 94,833,808	€ 94,833,808	max 18,785,037	
			mean 92,611	
			min ≈0	
without accessibility infrastructures (0.4)	€ 94,833,808	€ 94,833,808	max 1009,973	
			mean 42,374	
			min ≈0	

the therapeutic effects of the coastal environment (55 %), many still experience marginalization due to the lack of supportive infrastructure and services. Despite recognizing the importance of improving beach accessibility, 54 % of respondents reported being unwilling to pay for such enhancements in Greece. This likely reflects a widespread perception that accessibility improvements should be publicly funded, pointing to a broader demand for equal rights and social inclusion. The high per-visit cost may further discourage willingness to pay. This finding aligns with prior research [14], although research on the economic behavior of individuals with disabilities remains notably limited.

To reduce discrimination and improve the quality of life for individuals with disabilities, the European Union (EU) adopted the "Disability Strategy 2021–2030", in alignment with Article 26 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights [49]. Accessibility is a central pillar of this strategy, supported by concrete actions at both EU and national levels. In Greece, for example, the project "Creation of Integrated Tourist Accessible Marine Destinations" was co-funded by the European Union and the Greek Ministries of Tourism and Development and Investment, allocating €17 million to improve beach accessibility [42,50]. Despite these efforts, respondents still rated beach accessibility in Greece as poor and noted that this significantly affects their quality of life. Furthermore, respondents indicated that enhanced accessibility would positively impact their well-being. The analysis also revealed significant regional disparities in accessibility levels, especially when compared to local population sizes and incoming tourist volumes. Some regions remain comparatively underserved, highlighting the need for a more balanced and strategic distribution of accessibility infrastructure. At both national and regional levels, these findings can support more targeted policymaking, particularly in identifying high-priority areas for future investments. While all types of infrastructure were considered beneficial by respondents, the results highlight the urgent need to prioritize inclusive measures aligned with EU principles of equity and social inclusion.

Statistical data on individuals with disabilities, including wheelchair users, remain sparse in both Greece and the broader EU. In particular, Greece lacks validated and up-to-date data on the demographics, geographic distribution, and mobility characteristics of its wheelchair-using population. As a result, this study relied on older datasets and

stakeholder estimates [40,41] to assess the recreational value of beaches for this group. These data limitations may lead to discrepancies between estimated and actual population sizes, as well as final valuation figures. Similarly, data on disability-related tourism in Greece and Europe are either outdated or insufficiently detailed [48,51], limiting our ability to estimate inbound tourism value and potentially resulting in an underestimation of the total recreational value for wheelchair users RVW_u . While this study estimated option value based on the WTP of Greek residents, future research should include the WTP of international tourists with mobility impairments to better capture the full economic potential of inclusive tourism.

Data limitations also extend to accessibility infrastructure. Our mapping of access ramps, based on data from Seatrac and Seaccess, may underestimate the actual number and condition of ramps along the coastline. A comprehensive, regularly updated national database that includes ramp locations, condition, and features (e.g., disabled parking) would serve both users and policymakers, while enhancing monitoring of compliance with EU accessibility goals. Additionally, the final stage of our spatial analysis relied on crowdsourced images from flickr. While flickr is currently one of the most research-friendly platforms, it is used by a relatively narrow demographic and tends to emphasize tourist-centric content [52]. Consequently, beaches with higher numbers of uploaded images may be overrepresented, while those with limited online presence may be undervalued. This pattern was particularly evident in the case of a beach in Crete, which received the highest estimated recreational value, €18 million, driven by both extensive infrastructure and a high number of uploaded photos. The high visibility and popularity of such tourist-heavy beaches may disproportionately concentrate value. To mitigate these limitations, future research could integrate data from other social media platforms, such as Instagram, despite current restrictions on data access. Moreover, alternative mapping approaches tailored to the needs of individuals with mobility impairments could be explored [53,54]. Participatory mapping techniques using digital tools such as SeaSketch, could significantly enhance data quality and support more equitable and accurate assessments of accessibility across coastal areas [55].

The projected annual loss of €57 million in recreational value for wheelchair users, representing 24 % of the recreational value (RVW_u ;

Fig. 4. Valuation map of the recreational ecosystem service for wheelchair users along the Greek coastline. The color scale indicates the total annual recreational value per beach (€/beach/year), with darker shades of purple representing higher values.

€237 million/yr), underscores the substantial socio-economic impact of limited accessibility along Greece's coasts. Individuals who currently do not visit beaches due to physical or infrastructural barriers reported significantly higher anticipated expenditures under a scenario of improved accessibility, compared to those who already visit. This discrepancy may reflect the accumulated demand to reclaim missed recreational opportunities, a lack of real-life experience with accessible beaches leading to idealized projections, or more complex mobility needs (e.g., caregiver support or specialized transport) that raise expected costs. These findings reveal that exclusion from beach access not only limits rights to recreation and social participation but also suppresses considerable economic potential. The high estimated lost value

reflects both the intensity of unmet demand and the financial readiness or necessity of excluded individuals to participate in leisure activities under equitable conditions.

According to our cost-benefit analysis, this lost value could finance the construction of between 234 and 560 accessibility ramps. Investing in inclusive beach infrastructure is thus not only a matter of physical access but also a strategic step toward social justice, economic inclusion, and sustainable tourism. Addressing these accessibility gaps through targeted public policy and universal design represents a sound and essential investment with measurable returns for both individuals and society as a whole.

Fig. 5. Valuation map of the recreational ecosystem service for wheelchair users along the Greek coastline, with a focus on selected areas of interest: Crete Island, Rhodes Island, and the Attica–Athens region. The color scale represents the total annual recreational value per beach, with darker shades of purple indicating higher values. Blue bubbles indicate the locations of access ramps, while green bubbles represent the buffer zones reflecting the spatial impact of each ramp.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the significant economic value of beach recreation for wheelchair users in Greece. Despite national and EU-level commitments to improving accessibility, existing infrastructure remains inadequate to meet the needs of this population. Only a small proportion of the installed ramps offer comprehensive support and achieve high visitation rates. Our findings underscore the urgent need for enhanced accessibility to ensure equitable access to coastal

ecosystems and to promote inclusive tourism that benefits individuals with disabilities and the broader community.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mazaris Antonios D.: Writing – review & editing. **Valentini Stamatiadou:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Resources. **Adonis Velegrakis:** Writing – review & editing. **Theodoros Chalazas:**

Resources. **Stelios Katsanevakis**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Methodology.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT to improve the grammar and syntax of the text as non-native speakers. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as necessary and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program HORIZON-CL6–2021-BIODIV-01–04 under grant agreement No. 101059877 “GES4SEAS - Achieving Good Environmental Status for maintaining ecosystem Services, by Assessing integrated impacts of cumulative pressures”. The research was also supported by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership, in the context of the INSPIRE project under the 2021-2022 BiodivProtect joint call. It was co-funded by the European Commission (GA No. 101052342) and the following funding organisations: Agencia Estatal de Investigación (Spain), Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (Italy), Swiss National Science Foundation (Switzerland), Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Portugal), Der Wissenschaftsfonds (Austria), General Secretariat for Research and Innovation (Greece) and Salford University (UK).

We would like to express our gratitude to all of the participants who completed the questionnaire. Their contributions were instrumental to advancing our research.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2025.106805](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2025.106805).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] W.H. Organization, others, WHO global disability action plan 2014–2021: better health for all people with disability, World Health Organization, 2015.
- [2] K. Vornholt, et al., Disability and employment – overview and highlights, *Eur. J. Work Organ. Psychol.* 27 (2018) 40–55.
- [3] L.M. Banks, H. Kuper, S. Polack, Poverty and disability in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review, *PLOS ONE* 12 (2017) e0189996.
- [4] Y.-C. Chang, C.-F. Chen, Meeting the needs of disabled air passengers: factors that facilitate help from airlines and airports, *Tour. Manag.* 33 (2012) 529–536.
- [5] D.S. Raja, Background paper for the world development report, *Bridg. Disabil. Divid. Digit. Technol.* (2016).
- [6] S. Job, L. Heales, S. Obst, Oceans of opportunity for universal beach accessibility: an integrated model for health and wellbeing in people with disability, *Aust. N. Z. J. Public Health* 46 (2022) 252–254.
- [7] S. Job, L. Heales, S. Obst, Tides of Change—Barriers and facilitators to beach accessibility for older people and people with disability: an Australian community survey, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 20 (2023) 5651.
- [8] T. Ala-Hulkko, O. Kotavaara, J. Alahuhta, P. Helle, J. Hjort, Introducing accessibility analysis in mapping cultural ecosystem services, *Ecol. Indic.* 66 (2016) 416–427.
- [9] Disability in the EU: facts and figures. (<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/info/graphics/disability-eu-facts-figures/>).
- [10] Buhalis, D., Eichhorn, V., Michopoulou, E. & Miller, G. Accessibility market and stakeholder analysis. *University of Surrey y One Stop Shop for Accessible Tourism in Europe (OSSATE)* (2005).
- [11] K. Jindai, C.M. Nielson, B.A. Vorderstrasse, A.R. Quiñones, Multimorbidity and functional limitations among adults 65 or older, *NHANES 2005–2012*, *Prev. Chronic Dis.* 13 (2016) E151.
- [12] World Health Organization & World Bank, World report on disability, 325 (<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241564182>), 2011.
- [13] C. Twohig-Bennett, A. Jones, The health benefits of the great outdoors: a systematic review and meta-analysis of greenspace exposure and health outcomes, *Environ. Res.* 166 (2018) 628–637.
- [14] I. Wiesel, S. Weerts, M. LewisSand and Surf. Benefits, Elements and Pathways to Accessible Beaches.2022.
- [15] A. Ghermandi, Benefits of coastal recreation in Europe: identifying trade-offs and priority regions for sustainable management, *J. Environ. Manag.* 152 (2015) 218–229.
- [16] M.A. Huamantincio Cisneros, N.V. Revollo Sarmiento, C.A. Delrieux, M.C. Piccolo, G.M.E. Perillo, Beach carrying capacity assessment through image processing tools for coastal management, *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 130 (2016) 138–147.
- [17] J. Retka, et al., Assessing cultural ecosystem services of a large marine protected area through social media photographs, *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 176 (2019) 40–48.
- [18] I. Havinga, P.W. Bogaart, L. Hein, D. Tuia, Defining and spatially modelling cultural ecosystem services using crowdsourced data, *Ecosyst. Serv.* 43 (2020) 101091.
- [19] P. Prayaga, Estimating the value of beach recreation for locals in the great barrier reef marine park, Australia, *Econ. Anal. Policy* 53 (2017) 9–18.
- [20] X. Cheng, S. Van Damme, L. Li, P. Uyttenhove, Evaluation of cultural ecosystem services: a review of methods, *Ecosyst. Serv.* 37 (2019) 100925.
- [21] C. Lique, G. Zulian, I. Delgado, A. Stips, J. Maes, Assessment of coastal protection as an ecosystem service in Europe, *Ecol. Indic.* 30 (2013) 205–217.
- [22] G. Martínez Pastur, P.L. Peri, M.V. Lencinas, M. García-Llorente, B. Martín-López, Spatial patterns of cultural ecosystem services provision in Southern patagonia, *Landsc. Ecol.* 31 (2016) 383–399.
- [23] V. Stamatidou, A. Mazaris, Z. Mallios, S. Katsanevakis, Valuation and mapping of the recreational diving ecosystem service of the aegean sea, *Ecosyst. Serv.* 64 (2023) 101569.
- [24] A. Kosanic, J. Petzold, A systematic review of cultural ecosystem services and human wellbeing, *Ecosyst. Serv.* 45 (2020) 101168.
- [25] S.O. Lyu, Which accessible travel products are people with disabilities willing to pay more? A choice experiment, *Tour. Manag.* 59 (2017) 404–412.
- [26] M. Wolff, Taking one step further – advancing the measurement of Green and blue area accessibility using spatial network analysis, *Ecol. Indic.* 126 (2021) 107665.
- [27] J. Kim, S. Nicholls, Access for all? Beach access and equity in the detroit metropolitan area, *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 61 (2018) 1137–1161.
- [28] Mayordomo-Martínez, D. et al. Improving accessibility for people with disabilities: A case study on inclusive beach tourism. in *2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)* 1302–1305 (IEEE, 2019).
- [29] D. Lee, J. Kim, B. Thapa, T. Stein, Measuring beach accessibility for people with ambulatory difficulty, *J. Park Recreat. Adm.* 38 (2020).
- [30] L.A. Friedrich, et al., Using ecosystem service assessments to support participatory marine spatial planning, *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 188 (2020) 105121.
- [31] R. Pomeroy, F. Douvere, The engagement of stakeholders in the marine spatial planning process, *Mar. Policy* 32 (2008) 816–822.
- [32] I. Tammi, K. Mustajärvi, J. Rasinmäki, Integrating spatial valuation of ecosystem services into regional planning and development, *Ecosyst. Serv.* 26 (2017) 329–344.
- [33] National Statistical Authority of Greece. *Press Statement: People with Health Problems or Disabilities*. https://www.statistics.gr/el/statistics?p_id=documents_WAR_publicationsportlet_INSTANCE_qDQ8fBKKo4IN&p_p_lifecycle=2&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&p_p_cacheability=cacheLevelPage&p_p_col_id=column-2&p_p_col_count=4&p_p_col_pos=1&documents_WAR_publicationsportlet_INSTANCE_qDQ8fBKKo4IN_javax.faces.resource=document&documents_WAR_publicationsportlet_INSTANCE_qDQ8fBKKo4IN_in=downloadResources&documents_WAR_publicationsportlet_INSTANCE_qDQ8fBKKo4IN_documentID=108802&documents_WAR_publicationsportlet_INSTANCE_qDQ8fBKKo4IN_locale=el (2003).
- [34] Greek National Association of People with Ambulatory Disabilities. Population History. *EOKA* (<https://eoka.com.gr/istoriko/>).
- [35] Statistics - ELSTAT. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/statistics/-/publication/SJO12/2002>.
- [36] Bank of Greece. Travel services. <https://www.bankofgreece.gr/en/statistics/external-sector/balance-of-payments/travel-services> (2022).
- [37] U. Pascual, et al., The economics of valuing ecosystem services and biodiversity. in *The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity: Ecological and Economic Foundations*, Routledge, 2011.
- [38] Australian Bureau of Statistics. Sample Size Calculator. <https://www.abs.gov.au/websitedbs/D3310114.nsf/home/Sample+Size+Calculator>.
- [39] K. Arrow, et al., Rep. NOAA Panel Conting. *Valuat.* 58 (1993).
- [40] WHO releases new Wheelchair provision guidelines. <https://www.who.int/news/item/05-06-2023-who-releases-new-wheelchair-provision-guidelines>.
- [41] Hellenic Statistical Authority. 2021 Population-Housing Census - ELSTAT. <https://www.statistics.gr/en/2021-census-pop-hous> (2021).
- [42] Greek Ministry of Tourism. Recovery and Resilience Fund-Subproject 6 - Accessible beaches. <https://mintour.gov.gr/tameio-anakampsis-kai-anthektikotitas/> (2022).
- [43] Coastal Zones Land Cover/Land Use 2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly. <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/coastal-zones/coastal-zones-2018>.
- [44] S.A. Wood, A.D. Guerry, J.M. Silver, M. Lacayo, Using social media to quantify nature-based tourism and recreation, *Sci. Rep.* 3 (2013) 2976.
- [45] S. Mehvar, T. Filatova, A. Dastgheib, E. De Ruyter van Steveninck, R. Ranasinghe, Quantifying economic value of coastal ecosystem services: a review, *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 6 (2018) 5.

- [46] Stamatidou, V. et al. Monetary Valuation and Spatial Mapping of Recreational Ecosystem Service Along Greek Coasts. SSRN Scholarly Paper at <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4824975> (2024).
- [47] S. Darcy, B. Cameron, S. Pegg, Accessible tourism and sustainability: a discussion and case study, *J. Sustain. Tour.* 18 (2010) 515–537.
- [48] European Commission, Economic impact and travel patterns of accessible tourism in Europe – final report, 2012.
- [49] Union of equality: Strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities 2021–2030 - Employment, Social Affairs & Inclusion - European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1484&langId=en>.
- [50] AccessibleBeaches | Το Έργο. https://www.accessiblebeaches.gr/en_us/to-ergo/ (2024).
- [51] D. Buhalis, E. Michopoulou, S. Michailidis, I. Ambrose, Developing a One-Stop-Shop for the european disabled tourism market: technical and business challenges, *Innov. Knowl. Econ. Issues Appl. Case Stud.* (2005) 293.
- [52] T. Leppämäki, V. Heikinheimo, J. Eklund, A. Hausmann, T. Toivonen, The rise and fall of the social media platform flickr: implications for nature recreation research, *J. Outdoor Recreat. Tour.* 50 (2025) 100880.
- [53] T. Li, Z. Xiang, Y. Li, POIs-based public preferences mapping on imbalanced supply-demand of recreation services can support sustainable coastal beach management, *Front. Mar. Sci.* 11 (2024).
- [54] E.J. Provost, et al., Quantifying human use of sandy shores with aerial remote sensing technology: the sky is not the limit, *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 211 (2021) 105750.
- [55] C. Seijo Núñez, H. Calado, W. McClintock, A.J.F. Gil, C. Fonseca, 2021, Mapping recreational ecosystem services from stakeholders' perspective in the Azores.